

Optimum dosage of nitrogen and liquid organic fertilizer combination for lowland rice of Central Lombok, Indonesia

Fitria Zulhaedar, Lia Hadiawati and Yanti Triguna
NTB Assesment Institute for Agricultural Technology.*

Jl. Raya Peninjauan Narmada, West Lombok Regency, NTB, Indonesia

**Coressponding author : fitlia84@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Considering popularity of Liquid Organic Fertilizer (LOF) that environmental friendly to boost rice production, this study aimed to obtain optimum combination dosage of Nitrogen fertilizer (Urea) and LOF-Biourine for irrigated lowland rice grown during second planting season (March to June) at Dusun Punimbe of Ubung Village, Jonggat Subdistrict, Central Lombok, NTB, Indonesia. On-farm experiment was set on randomized block design that consist of seven fertilizer treatments were P1 application of 200 kg/ha Urea + 0% Biourine , P2 for 200 kg/ha urea + 10% Biourine, P3 for 200 kg/ha Urea + 20% Biourine, P4 for 150 kg/ha Urea + 10% Biourine, P5 for 150 kg/ha Urea + 20% Biourine, P6 for 100 kg/ha Urea + 10% Biourine, and P7 for 100 kg/ha + 20% Biourine, with five replication for each treatment. The results showed a variation on growth and yield of each treatment. Plan height was significantly higher at P5 compared to P1, whereas, P3 produced the highest number of a productive tiller that significantly different from other treatments. The number of filled grain was also highest at P3 but not significant to th others except at P4. The highest yield was obtained at P6, which indicating the optimum dosage. All in all, rice growth and yield was improved with supplemented nutrition from the LOF-Biourine.

Keywords: *rice, urea, biourin, growth, yield.*

INTRODUCTION

Rice is a major strategic commodity in Indonesia that its productivity is being promoted. Besides being a staple food or carbohydrate source for most of the Indonesian people, rice is one out of seven food commodities that highly prioritize by the government under food self-sufficiency program. Subowo et al. (2013) stated that various efforts carried out to achieve the program, including increasing cropping indexes, adaptation strategies to climate change through development of planting calendars, improving productivity, and controlling pests. Dynamic growth of harvested area and rice productivity in Indonesia over the past 20 years has shown an increase (BPS, 2015), but the growth rate of rice harvested area compared to the productivity growth is not equal, in which

the harvest area is higher than its productivity (Hermanto et al., 2015). This indicates that there are still great opportunities in increasing rice productivity through various efforts by not ruling out environmental conditions.

The application of technology, especially fertilization, is one of the critical sectors in increasing rice productivity. The availability of nutrients in the soil both macro and micro is relatively small, so the addition of nutrients through fertilization is needed for optimal production. Rice plants need macro nutrients, especially N, P and K (Fagi and Las, 2007), where the amount needed varies depending on specific site and targeted production - (Abdulrachman et al., 2009). According to Dobermann and Fairhurst (2000) in general the needs of N, P and K are 14.7 kg ;, 2.6 kg, and 14.5 kg for each ton of rice produced from fertilizers (organic and inorganic), soil, irrigation water, and crop residues.

Along with the development of technology, there are many types of fertilizers with varied nutrient content. On the other hand, the maximum use of inorganic fertilizers to increase rice production, especially for lowland rice, has an impact on soil chemical and physical properties (Hanum et al., 2016), such as higher soil acidity, especially from urea and ZA fertilizers and P-saturated soil and K, which is characterized by the high status of P and K nutrients (Priyanka et al.,). Land with the above conditions according to Setyorini et al. (2009) causing P and K fertilization less effective (no response), and high doses of N fertilization. For this reason, a balanced fertilization strategy is needed not only between the condition of the land, the needs of rice plants, and the right dose but also between organic and inorganic. The balanced fertilization between organic and inorganic fertilizers proved to be able to increase total N and cation exchange capacity (Doberman et al., 2003; Minardi et al., 2009; Susanto et al., 2013).

Liquid organic fertilizer (POC) is one of alternative fertilizer to improve crop yields while improving soil physical, chemical and biological properties (Moi et al., 2015; Jamilah, 2016; Setiawan, 2016). This study aims to obtain an inorganic fertilizing dose (urea) and liquid biourin organic fertilizer which is optimal for improving the growth and yield of rice plants in the paddy fields in the second planting season (MKI) of Punimbe Hamlet, Ubung Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency, NTB.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On-farm research was carried out on irrigated lowland rice area at Ubung Village, Jonggat Subdistrict, Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province. The experiment taking place during the second planting season (MK I) on March to May 2017. The materials used in this study

were new improved rice varieties Inpari 32, Urea fertilizer, NPK-Phonska fertilizer, Biourin liquid organic fertilizer obtained from the Tunas Maju farmer group Setanggor Village, West Praya District, Central Lombok Regency, with detail nutrient content listed in Table 1. Other material used in this study are medicines such as pesticides, herbicides, and fungicides, which are applied as needed based on crop development The row planting called *jajar legowo* 2: 1 applied at 20 cm pacing between and inter-row.

Table 1. Analysis result of liquid organic fertilizer (Biourin) produced by Tunas Maju Farmers Group at Setanggor village, West Praya District, Central Lombok Regency, NTB

Parameter	pH-H ₂ O	C-Organik	N-total	C/N ratio	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Unit		%	%		ppm	%
Result	9.67	1.02	0.08	12.75	0.05	1.57
Analysis						
Method	Elektroda	Wet ash	Kjeldahl	-	Sepctro	AAS

Note: the analysis result of soil and fertilizer laboratory of BPTP Balitbangtan NTB, 2016.

The experiment was lay out on randomized block design (RBD) with seven combinations of urea and organic liquid fertilizer (biourin) rate. Each treatment was replicated five times on the original plots size. The seven treatments were application of fertilizer rate at 200 kg/ha urea + 0% Biourin (P1); Urea 200 kg/ha + 10% Biourin (P2); Urea 200 kg/ha + Biourin 20% (P3); Urea 150 kg/ha + Biourin 10% (P4); Urea 150 kg/ha + Biourin 20% (P5); Urea 100 kg/ha + Biourin 10% (P6); and finally the use of urea dose as much as 100 kg/ha + Biourin 20% (P7). The use of biourin doses is only two levels/concentration, namely 10% and 20% based on the research of Tantawizal and Nazam (2017) in Setanggor Village, Central Lombok Regency in the second planting season (ICM) which shows that the highest rice growth and production is obtained from 10-15%. So in this study it is expected that an inorganic fertilizing formula (urea) will be obtained with an appropriate and optimum POC biourin. The use of the highest dose of urea in the treatment (200 kg/ha) was based on the recommendation of the integrated planting calendar (KATAM) for the Jonggat Subdistrict in the second planting season (MK) for rice crops that were planted without using additional organic fertilizer either straw or compost. Likewise with Phonska NPK fertilizer, using doses that were following KATAM recommendations and applied the same for all treatments that were 200 kg/ha, and applied twice that is 60-75% when the plant is ten days after transplanting.

The application of Urea and Biourin fertilizer given to each experimental plot was carried out as recommended in Based on integrated rice management, urea was applied as basal application and top dressing at age 15, 35 and 55 days after planting . Biourin was applied five times in weekly interval starting from 11 days after planting of 17 days seedling.

Table 2. The analysis result at study site (Punimbe hamblet, Ubung village, Jonggat district,, Central Lombok Regency, NTB)

Parameter	unit	testing result	Hara Status	method
pH-H ₂ O	-	7.16	neutral	pH-meter
N-NH ₄ ⁺	ppm	14.45	medium	Kjeldahl
N-NO ₃ ⁻	ppm	16.75	medium	Devarda Alloy
N-Total	%	0.17	low	Kjeldahl
C-organic	%	0.43	very low	Kurmish
sand	%	57		Hydrometer
silt	%	23		Hydrometer
clay	%	20		Hydrometer
class Tekstur			Sandy loam	
P ₂ O ₅ -Bray	ppm	7.86	medium	Bray
Exchangeable K	cmol./kg	0.44	medium	AAS
Exchangeable Na	cmol./kg	0.21	low	AAS
Exchangeable Ca	cmol./kg	6.29	medium	AAS
Exchangeable Mg	cmol./kg	0.74	low	AAS
P ₂ O ₅ -Bray	-	7.16	neutral	pH-meter
CEC	cmol./kg	12.58	low	Percolations

Note: the analysis result of soil and fertilizer laboratory of BPTP Balitbangta NTB, 2016.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The balanced fertilization is one of the crucial efforts to increase rice production and productivity. Application of fertilizers that based on the biophysical and stage of crop development is not only increased production and productivity, but also maintain and even improve soil fertility. In turn, the availability of nutrients for plants can always be maintained. Cobination of biourin organic liquid fertilizer and urea fertilizer is one of the methods to provide additional nutrients to the soil and crop so that it is expected to improve

soil physical, chemical and biological properties as well as stimulate growth and yield of rice in on-farm site.

Vegetative Parameters

The significant variation was seen of plant height and number of tillers at 30 days after planting (DAP), 60 DAP, and harvest. Common minimum fertilizer rate by local farmer was 250 kg/ha urea and 250 kg/ha NPK-Phonska. Some farmers even gave a higher dose of urea, but from the interviews, it was found that the production obtained remained the same despite the addition of the dose of urea. This is one reason for using 200 kg/ha of urea as the highest dose in the study. The results showed that medium urea rates at 150 kg/ha were not significantly different some vegetative parameter compared to the highest rate of urea at 200 kg/ha.

Table 3. The statistic analysis result of vegetative parameter of rice plant at study site , Punimbe hamblet, Ubung village, Jonggat district, Central Lombok Regency, NTB

treatment	Height of Plant 30 HST	number of saplings 30 HST	Height of Plant 60 HST	number of saplings 60 HST	Height of Harvest Plant	Number of productive saplings	number of total saplings (harvest)
P1	46.6ab	14.6ab	75.2c	25.8b	91.6ab	18.8ab	20.2b
P2	55.6c	14.2ab	68.6b	14.6a	95.4bc	16.6ab	17.6ab
P3	51.6bc	16.8bc	73b	19.8ab	95.2bc	24c	24.4c
P4	51.4bc	17.8c	75.6c	24.4b	91.6ab	15.8ab	16.4a
P5	49.6ab	16.6bc	68.8b	23.2b	98.4c	19.4b	20.8bc
P6	46.2ab	16.6bc	67.2ab	19.8ab	90a	15.2a	19.4ab
P7	45.6a	13a	61.6a	16.4a	94.2b	17.2ab	17.6ab
l.s.d.	5.224	3.277	6.32	6.437	3.987	4.154	3.755

note: the number which followed by the same word at the same column show that is not significantly different at LSD test level 5%; P1 (urea 200 kg/ha); P2 (urea 200 kg/ha+biourin 10%); P3 (urea 200 kg/ha+biourin 20%); P4 (urea 150 kg/ha+10%); P5 (urea 150 kg/ha+biourin 20%); P6 (urea 100 kg/ha+biourin 10%); P7 (urea 100 kg/ha+20%).

Table 3 shows that there were significant differences between treatments in each parameter. Plant height at 30 DAP was the highest at the highest urea rate in P2 and P3, but similar to the height at 150 kg/ha rate of urea. Shorter growth was seen at the lowest urea rate in P6 and P7. In line with the results. Siregar and Marzuki (2011) reported that N uptake by plants which has an impact on its growth is strongly influenced by the availability of N in the soil due to fertilization treatment. The highest number of tillers at 30 was obtained at some urea rate with additional Biourin.. It is likely available nitrogen was

increased presumably due to the presence of P and K nutrients in Biourin that for root development and the growth of plant tissues

Figure 1. The average height of productive plant (a), number of total saplings (b) and number of productive saplings (c)

Plant height at harvest showed a normal distribution for all treatment except for treatment P5 and P6. The application of urea at medium dose (150 kg/ha) and the highest biourin dose (20%) produced the highest plant height. In contrast, the lowest dose of urea (100 kg/ha) combined with the lowest dose biourin (10%) showed the lowest plant height (figure 1.a). Whereas, the distribution of the average number of tillers (figure 1.b) shows that tiller number in P3 and P4 spread beyond the average treatment. The data distribution of productive tiller shows 86% of the data is on the average threshold, while the other 14% are above the average that found in P3 (200 kg/ha Urea + 20% biourin). This shows that combination of urea and biourin at the highest concentration could optimize the growth of rice.

Yield Component

Variation on yield component was shown in each treatment, especially total number of grains, number of filled grains, and number of unfilled grains. The results showed that the panicle length was not significantly different between treatments, even though the P3 and P5 gave the highest value. Whereas, total number of grain number of filled grain, and number of unfilled grain show a significant difference between treatments.

Table 4. The analysis result of the variation on yield components of rice at study site

treatment	panicle length (cm)	total number of grain	number of filled grain	number empty grain
P1	20.87	132.3abc	121.5a	10.8ab
P2	20.93	136.5a	122.9a	13.5a
P3	21.6	136.1ab	124.2a	11.9ab
P4	20.33	115.9c	102.1b	13.9a
P5	21	124.7abc	120.1ab	4.6b
P6	20.93	117.3bc	106.3ab	11.1ab
P7	20.4	124.9abc	110.3ab	14.7a
l.s.d.	1.301	19.07	18	7.79
notation	ns	**	*	*

note : the number which followed by the same alphabet at the same column show that is not significantly different at LSD test level 5%; P1 (urea 200 kg/ha); P2 (urea 200 kg/ha+biourin 10%); P3 (urea 200 kg/ha+biourin 20%); P4 (urea 150 kg/ha+10%); P5 (urea 150 kg/ha+biourin 20%); P6 (urea 100 kg/ha+biourin 10%); P7 (urea 100 kg/ha+20%).

The highest total number of grain obtained from the highest dose of urea fertilizer in P1, P2, and P3, but not significantly different from other treatments. While number of filled grain at the highest urea dose (P1 and P2) was only significantly to the treatment at medium dose of urea+biourin 10% (P4), but not significantly different from other treatments (P5, P6 and P7), namely medium dose urea plus 20% biourin and low dose urea plus biourin 10% and 20%.

Picture 2: Number of tiller and grain yield in harvested plot area at some rate of urea fertilizer and biourin combination

The results of regression analysis between the grain yield and hills number in 10 m² harvested plot area for multiple R values and the coefficient of determination were 0.90 and 0.82. This indicates that the variable number of hills is positively correlated with grain yield. The highest number of hills was obtained at P2 (Urea 200 kg/ha + biourin 10%), but the highest grain yield was obtained at P6 (urea 100 kg/ha + biourin 10%).

Average grain yield at additional 10% biourin was produced a higher yield (6.52 kg) compared to higher dose at 20% biourin (6.2 kg). Whereas, plot grain yield of urea fertilizer at rate 200 kg/ha; 150 kg/ha; and 100 kg/ha was 5.62 kg, 6.33 kg, and 6.03 kg respectively. In P1 at the highest dose of urea 20 kg/ha without the addition of biourin showed the lowest plot grain yield at 5.47 kg. This illustrates that the addition of biourin has an impact on increasing rice grain yield. In other words, the complex organic nutrient content and microorganisms in biourin not only improving availability of nutrients, including nitrogen, but also act as plant growth regulator. Generally, combination of urea and biourin are complementary in stimulating growth and yield of plants, in line with the results obtained from Dewanto et al., (2013).

Picture 3. Rice plant production (t/ha) at treatment combination of urea fertilizer combined with POC biourin.

Generally, there was variation of rice grain yield between treatments. Addition of biourin with a concentration of 10% on urea fertilization at a dose of 100 kg/ha gave the highest yield (7.14 ton/ha). On the other hand the application of urea fertilizer at a dose of 200 kg/ha without the addition of biourin showed lower yields (5.48 ton/ha). Overall for all urea doses, the addition of biourin with a 10% concentration gave better results compared to 20%. The lack of response to the growth and yield of plants against high doses of urea is thought to be due to the low cation exchange capacity, so the addition of organic matter is one of the effective methods in increasing the root absorption capacity of nutrients in the soil solution. This can be seen from the high response of growth and yield of rice plants at the study site to the addition of biourin, especially at a concentration of 10% Biourin.

CONCLUSIONS

There is considerable variation in growth and yield for each treatment. In average, the highest plant height was obtained from moderate urea dose (150 kg/ha) plus 20% biourin, significantly different from plants given urea with the highest dose of urea (200 kg/ha) without biourin. The highest number of productive tillers in P3 (200 kg/ha+Biourin 20% was significantly different from other treatments. The highest number of filled grains at P3 was not significantly different from other treatments except P4 (Urea 150 kg/ha+Biourin 10%). Whereas, grain yield obtained the highest results on P6 (Urea 100 kg/ha+Biourin

10%). So, it can be concluded that the addition of biourin can make efficient use of urea while increasing the growth and yield of rice

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was funded by the DIPA AIAT NTB, Ministry of Agriculture. We would like to express our wholeheartedly thank to Dr. Ahmad Suriadi, SP. M.Agr.Sc. as a head of the programme for the guidance during the research.

REFERENCES

- Abdulrachman, S., Hasil Sembiring and Suyamto. 2009. Pemupukan Tanaman Padi. Balai Besar Penelitian Tanaman Padi. Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Tanaman Pangan. http://www.litbang.pertanian.go.id/special/padi/bbpadi_2009_itp_05.pdf. 43p (123-124).
- Badan Pusat Statistik. 2017. Luas panen, produktivitas dan produksi tanaman pangan menurut provinsi, <https://www.bps.go.id/dynamic/table/2019/04/15/1608/luas-panen-produksi-dan-produktivitas-padi-menurut-provinsi-2018.html>. diunduh pada tanggal 23 September 2017.
- Dewanto, Frobel G., J.J.M.R. Londok., R.A.V. Tuturoong and W.B. Kaunang. 2013. The effect of inorganic and organic fertilization on corn crop production as a feed source. *Zootek Journal*, **32**: 8pp.
- Doberman, A. and T. Fairhurst. 2000. Rice: Nutrient Disorders and Nutrient Management. Makati: International Rice Research Institute. 191p.
- Doberman A, C. Witt, and D. Dawe. 2003. Performance of site-specific nutrient management in intensive rice cropping system of Asia. *Better Crops International*. **16**: 25-30.
- Fagi, A. M. and Las I. 2007. Equip farmers with advanced technology based on local wisdom in the era of sustainable green revolution. In Kasryno, F., E. Pasandaran and A. M. Fagi (Eds). Reversing the Flow Reaping the Independence of Farmers. Padi Indonesia Foundation, Jakarta
- Hanum, H., Hardy Guchy and Jamilah. 2016. Effect of inorganic and organic fertilizers on the chemical properties of soil in paddy fields with SRI and conventional cropping systems. Proceedings of Seminas National

- Suboptimal Land 2016, Palembang 20-21 Oktober 2016. ISBN: 979-587-659-7. 10p.
- Hermanto, Andi., Teguh Bharata Adji, Noor Akhmad Setiawan. 2015. Recurrent neural network language model for English-Indonesia Machine Translation: Experimental study. International Conference on Science in Information Technology (ICSITech). IEEE.
- Jamilah. 2016. Effect of liquid organic fertilizer from *C.odorata* on potassium nutrient uptake and lading rice yield . *Bibiet Journal*, **1**(1). 17-26.
- Minardi, S., Joko Winarno and Abror Hanif Nur Abdillah. 2009. The effect of balancing organic fertilizers and inorganic fertilizers on the chemical properties of andisol tawangmangu soil and the results of carrot plants (*Daucus carota L.*). *Journal of Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta* 57126. 6p.
- Moi, Anastasia R., Dingse Pandiangan, Parluhutan Siahaan and Agustina M. Tangapo. 2015. Testing of liquid organic fertilizer from water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) to the growth of mustard plants (*Brassica juncea*). *Online Journal of MIPA UNSRAT* 4(1). 15-19.
- Tantawizal and Moh. Nazam. 2017. The use of biourin liquid organic fertilizer in an effort to reduce the use of urea fertilizer in rice plants in Central Lombok Regency. Paper presented at the National Seminar on Accelerating the Transfer of Agricultural Technology Supporting Agricultural Revitalization and Regional Development , Denpasar Bali 5-6 September 2017.
- Priyanka, Siti Nisrina Hasna, Oka Violani and R. Gumbira W. (2017). The effect of using inorganic fertilizers without balanced organic fertilizers and biological fertilizers for the health of soil and plants. http://www.academia.edu/11485320/PENGARUH_PENGGUNAAN_PUPUK_ANORGANIK_TANPA_DIIMBANGI_PUPUK_ORGANIK_DAN_PUPUK_HAYATI_BAGI_KESEHATAN_TANAH_DAN_TANAMAN 11p.
- Setiawan, Chandra Kurnia. 2016. The effect of the concentration of liquid organic fertilizer enriched by osmotoleran rhizobacteria on the growth and yield of rice plants under drought stress conditions. . *Planta Tropika Journal of Agro Science*, **4** (2). 65-74.
- Setyorini, D., Sri Rochayati and Irsal Las. 2010. Agriculture in paddy field ecosystems. Reversing the trends in the degradation of land and water resources, chapter iii. Agriculture in paddy field ecosystems. Jakarta

Agricultural Research Agency. IPB Press, Campus of IPB Taman Kencana Bogor. 19p (35-36).

Siregar, Adelina, and Ilyas Marzuki. 2011. Efficiency of urea fertilization on uptake and increase in lowland rice production (*Oryza sativa L.*). *Journal of Budidaya Pertanian*, 7 (2). 5p (107-112).

Subowo, Jati Purwani and Sri Rochayati. 2013. Prospects and challenges of developing Biofertilizer to improve soil fertility. *Journal of Sumberdaya Lahan*, 7 No. 1. 12p.

Susanto, A. N., P. S. Marthen dan D. W. Edwen. 2013. Location-specific nutrient management study of irrigated paddy rice in Buru Regency. *Journal of Pengkajian dan Pengembangan Teknologi Pertanian*, 16(1): 20-31.